

Rapid Prototyping Platform for Multi-Stakeholder Involvement in the Design of User Interaction

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Abstract. Over the last couple of years, human oriented manufacturing, also called social manufacturing, became an ever more important aim in the transition into an industry 4.0. One of the best ways of doing that is to bring the end users, manufactures, and other participants from the production and design process closer together, so they can all make improved and socially sustainable products a reality. Prototyping, as a part of the design thinking process, plays a significant role in the physical and virtual implementation of a concept and is an essential phase during the collaborative design and search for new ideas. Depending on the project objectives and the collaborator skills and preferences, different forms of prototyping can be applied. This paper describes a prototyping platform that makes use of the combination of different prototyping techniques. The proposed approach for collaborative prototyping is illustrated with an example of the idea development for several interaction scenarios of different complexity.

Keywords: Collaborative Prototyping, Human-Computer Interaction, Remote Collaboration, Prototyping Platform.

1 Introduction

This research was partially funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement no. 870037 (iPRODUCE project [1]). During this project a prototype called Generative Design Platform (GDP) was developed to support both “makers” (engineers, designers, manufacturers) and consumers in their collaborative activities like co-design, collaborative prototyping, and testing [2]. In the current study, the GDP is extended via integration with external tools and components.

Over the last couple of years, human oriented manufacturing, also called social manufacturing, became an ever more important aim in the transition into an industry 4.0 [3]. Essentially, it puts the human being in the forefront when thinking about improving the manufacturing processes. One of the best ways of doing that is to bring the end users, manufactures, and possibly other participants from the production and design process closer together, so they can all make improved and socially sustainable products a reality.

Design Thinking is a widely accepted user centric iterative process for the effective discovery of the user wishes, problem solving, and idea generation [4]. It is suited for the objectives of social manufacturing. Design thinking consists of six main steps: empathize, define, ideate, prototype, test, and implement. Prototyping, as a part of the design thinking process, plays a significant role in the physical and virtual implementation of a concept for the early evaluation and selection of the proper solution. This paper focuses on the prototype phase by discussing different types of prototypes and proposing a methodology for their effective combination with an example of a prototyping framework and its application to a set of scenarios simulating a shopfloor with IoT features.

Transforming customer wishes into the final product is tricky and often goes a long way through different stages. One reason is because the end users lack technical understanding needed to specify requirements at the level, so that developers can proceed directly to implementation. During collaborative and co-creation sessions project stakeholders strive for different objectives. While low fidelity prototypes (as paper prototypes) are easily understandable and exploitable by non-technical stakeholders, they often cannot capture essential functionality details needed for developers. On the other hands, there are too many efforts implied for technical developers when implementing high fidelity prototypes. This coupled with the shortage on technical staff leads to a strong desire to shift as many tasks as possible away from the developers to other stakeholder often with less or no technical skills. Also, the rising standards on quality and usability of the applications request early involvement of the end users and other stakeholders in the design and prototyping of the applications.

The approach of this research aims to mitigate the hurdles for non-technical persons to participate in the feasibility study of interaction concepts during early prototyping phase. Our other target is to make the development of prototypes modular and easily extendable. To reach this, we propose to use resources that are simple enough to be quickly taught to different stakeholders and allow to build “executable” prototypes fast. Even technically skilled staff can benefit, as they can show very quickly several alternatives to the end customers to explain the possibilities of (new) technologies and details they need for the implementation. Our contribution illustrates how collaborative interaction can be prototyped fast and tested with several scenarios.

To apply rapid prototyping involving more stakeholders into the development of concepts for “collaborative interactions”, we built a Rapid Prototyping Platform (RapPP). While Section 2 provides a general consideration about the existing prototyping methods, the implementation of our platform will be explained in Section 3 and exemplified with a use case for an “interactive” shopfloor prototyping in Section 4. Section 5 summarizes our experience during the prototyping of the platform and testing it with different user interaction scenarios.

2 Prototyping Methods

One main task during the user centric design is the identification of the user needs, which can be challenging as the end users often lack the technological understanding.

This is especially a case in the new technology areas, where users may even have no idea what is possible to expect. It can be very difficult for them to discover requirements, what they can wish from the technologies they never heard before or from their combination or integration into existing tools.

Prototypes provide concrete representations of design ideas and give designers, users, developers, and managers an early insight into how the new system will look and feel. They have great potential because they can make it easier to express your thoughts, come up with new ideas, get valuable customer assessments, prove hypotheses and in addition to that they are cheap and expandable. Depending on the project objectives and the development state, different forms and types of prototyping can be applied [19, 20]. Moreover, each type of prototyping requires different skills (e.g., 3D modelling, additive manufacturing, hardware, or software knowledge) and may need an access to specific equipment, like additive / subtractive manufacturing devices (3D printer or laser cutter), or other resources (like licenses).

According to [20] the user prototypes are mostly created with a purpose to test a concept with customers and received direct feedback. Depending on the set objectives, engineers drive technical feasibility or improve data flows in live-data prototypes, therefore, this stakeholder group strives for either feasibility or live-data prototypes. For this reason, engineers often underestimate the importance of design principles. Feasibility prototypes are made to test the viability and functionality of the product. Live-data prototypes intend to test the digital features and functionalities of a program or a solution. Project managers have to take all three prototyping types into consideration. Thus, different prototyping techniques can help to bring end customers and technical developers closer to the mutual understanding.

Our contribution is devoted to a rapid prototyping example and illustrates how collaborative interaction can be tested for a selected case study. Rapid prototyping [6] is quick and inexpensive technique. On the other hand, it requires a more thought-out concept but can therefore evolve with further development into a finalized system. In addition to that, there is also iterative prototyping which is particularly attractive if the goal is to continuously improve ideas and learn from mistakes [5].

Figure 1 illustrates another dimension of the prototyping approaches and technologies used during our study to visualize and evaluate new ideas.

Fig. 1. Approaches and sample technologies considered in our Prototyping Framework.

Paper prototyping [21] is an effective tool to visualize an idea in the shortest time. It belongs to the most common approaches for low-fidelity prototypes in the initial stage and requires no additional training or expensive specialized equipment. So, this approach is low-cost, which is an important factor for sustainable development. In our research, paper prototyping was applied to create a cardboard robot arm evaluating the range of motion, to simulate a shopfloor environment and working employees with the help of SAP Scenes [17]. Best practice includes usage of paper prototyping not only for user acceptance evaluation, but also for feasibility testing.

Virtual prototyping requires intermediate knowledge of 3D modelling. It may involve additional cost related to software licenses. In our research, Rhinoceros [11] with its plugin Grasshopper [12] was used to create and visualize parametric 3D models of smart products. This approach was useful to develop a movement simulation and design selection by means of visual scripting. Co-Spaces [18] were used to simulate the environment of a shopfloor and to test safety rules in potentially dangerous situations that may happen if humans will work together with different autonomously moving robots or other equipment. The best practice includes using virtual prototyping for initial concepts development and their simulation.

Industrial prototyping involves advanced knowledge of 3D/2D modelling, CAD, and other software. It often involves additional cost caused by expensive software licenses and access to high-tech devices (3D printer, laser cutter, CNC machine). This type of prototyping drives innovation with additive and subtractive manufacturing approaches. In our study for the aim of rapid prototyping, we used ready 3D models from the 3D community Thingiverse [22] and printed them with Ultimaker [23], a 3D printer series. In this regard, the best practice involves feasibility testing but can also involve user acceptance testing.

Electronic prototyping requires knowledge in electronics and hardware (HW) programming. Moreover, it often involves additional costs needed for electronics, like microcontrollers, sensorics, motors, and other pieces of HW, but may also need a 3D printer or similar equipment to mount electronic components together. In our research project, Arduino [13] and micro:bit [14] microcontrollers with diverse sensors and actuators were used to check new interaction concepts including both human-machine (HMI) and machine-to-machine interaction (MMI). The best practice for this technique involves mainly feasibility testing.

3 Prototyping Platform

Different skills and backgrounds of stakeholders in combination with their different objectives in prototyping can have unpredictable consequences. Therefore, there is a strong need to combine collective efforts and improve stakeholder management during prototyping sessions.

In our case study we assume a situation we really faced in our project. The involved tools and components were originally designed as single-user applications. Our project partners reflected the wish for multi-player mode of the collaboration. This means they wanted that several persons participate simultaneously in one session to design 3D products. When asked for exact requirements and expectations on such collaboration, they only pointed to the existing online text editing tool.

To investigate the potentials of remote interaction of multiple users with a system of IoT devices we have built a prototyping framework – Rapid Prototyping Platform (RapPP) – combining several types of prototypes, UIs, and their connections. To keep the efforts low, we reused existing UIs, connecting different tools within this framework. Moreover, we applied visual scripting techniques ([12, 7, 15]) for quick modifications within different components of the framework, in particular for virtual and electronic prototypes. It is continuously being extended with further features needed to make the collaboration easier and more effective or to cover further collaboration scenarios.

There are several principles implemented in this platform that help to reach the targets:

- Integration of social platforms into the process of the user collaboration to reuse existing user interfaces (UIs) during the prototyping and to study the “natural” user interaction within their familiar environment.
- Different low-code/no-code techniques – like Visual scripting, graphical programming – to accelerate the creation of executable prototype for virtual and physical visualization of possible outcomes of the user interaction.
- Usage of the chat-bot technology by combining the social network applications with the GDP’s component for natural language processing (NLP). This makes the human interaction effective in the prototyping phase because such interaction is flexible enough without the need to constantly update the interface.
- Integration of MQTT messaging [9] to capture the machine-to-machine communication and combine this with the human inputs.

One of the main achievements of the applied approach is the involvement of existing user interfaces (UI) into different steps of prototyping, which makes it easier for the users to participate in the prototyping activities by interacting over the familiar front ends, also remotely over the internet. This was discovered to be essential for collaborative prototyping. Another result of our research is the show case how to extend typical single player applications (like 3D modeling, NLP tool) to handle multi-player mode necessary for real collaborative user interaction, including different locations.

During this research, we studied different usage possibilities for our GDP. We have integrated it with other UIs and used it as Digital Twin connected to the physical prototypes.

Figure 2 below gives an overview of the overall structure of the RapPP and dependencies among its components as well as with other tools.

Fig. 2. RapPP overview.

The collection of all inputs from different interfaces is performed within the RapPP server. The server is implemented with visual scripting tool Node-RED [7]. We decided to use Node-RED for the server prototyping, because it applies low code paradigm with a steep learning curve, contains many libraries for easy integration with other tools/interfaces (Slack, Twitter, Airtable, Alexa, and many other). For the current case study, we considered Slack [8] as an example of the social interaction interface. So, for the prototype we don't need to care about user management, security, and similar features. Users can organize themselves in groups, called channels in Slack's workspaces, those identifying different projects or products. Users need only to configure a special chat-bot, an integration feature of Slack. The RapPP server communicates with this chat-bot listening for any textual inputs from the participants. It then processes these texts by calling external NLP (Natural Language Processing) application and saving the structured results on an external data base.

To allow potential algorithms, like other devices (including those from the internet) or artificial intelligence, to interact with the created HW prototype, we also integrated the MQTT communication within the RapPP server. To make it possible for humans to test this type of interaction, we constructed very simple dashboards on mobile devices that can be easily updated while concepts are evolving during the prototyping phase.

The server finally generates the reply to confirm the reception of the command or wish. In addition to the reply to the Slack's users, the server can send the reply as an MQTT message to be processed by any device subscribed to such messages. 3D/CAD/Digital Twin applications obtain the information directly from the external data base where structured information from all inputs is stored. The Slack interface was selected to add the multi-user interaction feature to our evaluation scenarios, as several participants can be invited to one channel and contribute to the same project simultaneously while observing the contributions of each other.

Currently, for the natural language processing we integrated our own tool Spatial Instructor, a component from the GDP, to understand commands from the collaborators. But any other can be also connected via the web-request node within the server implementation. The results from Spatial Instructor are structured texts with extracted parameter values that are mapped to the structure defined within the data base. The NLP component is optional one. The initial version of the RapPP was developed without the text analysis. The users needed to know the exact syntax of the command to control the digital twin and field devices. The NLP component was added to improve the usability of the RapPP prototype to make it easier for the users to specify their wishes in non-structural way and concentrate more on the interaction itself.

We selected an existing application Airtable [10] as our external data base, because it already has integration with Node-RED and provides a user-friendly no-code definition of the necessary data structure that we need within our case study. The data model of the current case study is simple, reflecting only spatial properties of the components of a 3D model and few commands to control simple robot prototypes.

The data from the Airtable data base can be accessed by existing 3D applications. In our case study, we used Rhinoceros [11] with Grasshopper [12] as tools for the digital twin definition, that access the structured data from Airtable over its REST API and perform the user commands. Grasshopper is another example of visual scripting tool within a 3D modeling application. Our digital twin implementation is based on the Grasshopper scripts developed as part of another GDP's component, 3D Configurator. These visual scripts contain the 3D model of a robot arm with the positioning information, different design options, and definition of the connection to the corresponding physical prototype. This allows to run user commands from Slack in the real world to check different possible scenarios of human interaction with different machines including simultaneous contributions.

The main physical prototype of a robot arm, developed with 3D printing and built based on a popular HW prototyping platform Arduino [13], was connected to its virtual presentation. This provided a real-time command execution, where the participants had an opportunity to test a collaborative interaction in nearly real-time, synchronously on the physical device and its digital twin.

We also built connections to further simple electronic examples developed on the basis of educational platform micro:bit [14] with the possibility for graphical programming [15]. The examples included an LED stripe attached to the paper prototype of a dashboard, small mobile robots running between SAP Scenes' objects, wearable electronics attached to "human" objects to capture the state of the human models. This swarm of the HW prototypes communicating wirelessly with each other can be extended at any point of time. The user commands from Slack are broadcasted to all participating devices, which may react on those commands or ignore them. This extendable HW swarm serves to check even more different scenarios of interaction among humans and machines.

4 Case Study: Prototyping an IoT Shopfloor

While developing the prototyping platform RapPP, we have designed a case study to check the feasibility of the following aspects, including their usability for non-technical stakeholders:

- Combination of different prototyping techniques in one system to be performed by different stakeholders with different skills.
- Application of low-code and low-cost paradigms with visual scripting, graphical programming, and educational HW platforms to involve more participants from different user groups into the prototyping process.
- Reuse of existing User Interfaces (UI) to allow a fast definition and check of new concepts but also to see possible challenges of the human-machine interaction before a specific application is implemented.

To cover these aspects, a team of different stakeholders with different skills and roles started to develop new concepts for the future shopfloors exploiting IoT technologies for an effective and safe interaction between humans and devices. In this shopfloor prototype, humans could interact directly with robots and other smart equipment and could command devices remotely, including the internet communication from remote locations, to correct the machines' behavior or to provide (new) tasks. The actual tests within real shopfloors are too expensive to perform, disturbing the work, and can be dangerous when introducing new devices/robots among humans. So, the initial tests for possible challenges in the interaction between multiple agents in a shared room were designed with small robots and human models on a small surface.

We have started with the paper prototype with SAP Scenes to set up environment and to define basic movements for the problem statement. After that, we added simple electronics of the following four types simulating different interactions with different hazard potentials:

- LED Dashboard (no real hazard for human),
- Robot arms (partially fixed, restricted hazards for humans),
- Fully mobile robots (the most potential for hazardous situations),

- Wearables for the human objects, interacting with other electronics to check different safety treatments.

Each device type got its own simple program to react on different signals, either sent as commands from the users over the Slack interface or as indicators for specific situations within the shopfloor. All commands from Slack, stored in the Airtable data base as described in the previous section, were accessed by the Grasshopper scripts (developed as parts of the GDP) over the web-interface. As an example, one such script defines a parametric model with the state of the digital twin corresponding to the electronic prototype of a robot arm. This digital twin allows to modify both design and spatial positioning of the robot arm by a team of the Slack users. Because this digital twin was connected to the electronic prototype, they both reacted synchronously on the commands from the users. But, due to the digital nature of the digital twin, it was also possible for remote users to test different designs of the digital robot arm: color schemes, textures, lights. So, our first tested scenario (Figure 3) was the internet user interaction for the decisions on the design presented digitally.

Fig. 3. Usage scenario I: user interaction for design definition.

While testing this scenario for the feasibility of the technologies integration, we observed that the RapPP was able to capture all requests from a team members in a FIFO (first in first processed) manner. So, only the latest decision was visible in the collaborative result. The process of collecting and storing the inputs as well as the digital twin needed to be extended to keep and visualize the information about the contributors and all the results from all contributors to visualize all design proposals individually. The team members must then decide, which options to keep for the resulting device.

After the first simple scenario test, we extended the scene with more electronic elements to check more complex system behavior, where more devices reacted to the

commands from the Slack’s users by starting or changing motion and lighting feedback (Figure 4). During this experiment, we iteratively extended the electronic prototypes adding some micro:bit controllers to further elements on the scene. The objects from the paper prototyping phase, being extended with the electronics, provided a better and fast visualization for the target system functionality. New robots were 3D printed (corresponding to industrial prototyping) and added to the testbed to check collaboration effects among different types of robots. This gave us inputs for the further ideas about the possible needs for controls within shopfloor: setting up limits, feedback with lights and audio output on different devices, including wearable electronics attached to the human objects.

Fig. 4. Usage scenario II: user interaction with the IoT devices in a shopfloor.

Parallel to all those digital and electronic tests for functional feasibility, a user with the role of safety engineer together with a designer developed a virtual and executable model illustrating cases that can happen when all those devices interact with humans within a shopfloor. So, the potential safety issues were modeled within an educational environment with virtual reality features [18] (virtual prototyping). This provided a quick spatial and dynamic visualization of new functionalities corresponding to the behavior observed during the incremental electronic tests. Then, new features were added to several elements within the electronic prototype to test the feasibility of new concepts for the safety control. These additional features included communication between the wearable electronics on the human object with the mobile robots and the dashboard. We tried and tested different alarm situations, defining how devices should react.

An example of prototype phases for the described IoT shopfloor use case is shown on Figure 5.

Fig. 5. An example of prototypes for physical (paper + electronics) and virtual simulation of safety aspects (usage scenario III).

Our project team tested the “executable” prototypes remotely over the internet operating HW and virtual prototypes collectively. This helped to analyze the robot arm operation in combination with other types of IoT devices. Due to the different levels of users’ skills, the project required a solution with an easy and understandable interface for a better communication among the team members. With the goal to make the prototype testing accessible and understandable for all participants, several intuitive user interfaces such as tabular interfaces (defined within Airtable) and textual inputs (within the social platform Slack) were used for commands to operate the prototypes remotely. This approach appears to be especially useful for project members without the necessary technical background.

As a result of our experiment, it was detected that multiple participants with different skills and different objectives can effectively collaborate during a multi-user session and develop new concepts together. The necessary condition is that each stakeholder participates in this process by means of a simple UI suitable for this person, his/her interests, skills, and preferences. For the better usability, the RapPP needed to be extended with more visualization features and feedback mechanisms.

The aspects that were important for collaborative interaction and being covered by the RapPP include the following:

- Several levels of prototyping,
- Combination of Machine-to-Machine and Human-to-Machine interaction,
- Multi-user collaboration over different channels,
- Testing spatial properties of the functioning devices and other objects,
- Unpredictability and, thus, complexity of the multi-agent interaction,
- Extendibility in the future,
- Low code / low costs,
- Combination of local interaction and global one over the internet.

The team participating in the RapPP prototyping contained different roles and skills – designers, SW developers, HW developers, project manager – thus, participants with and without technical skills.

5 Conclusion

During our study, we considered different prototyping techniques and tools. Because different stakeholders have different skill sets and prefer different tools according to the Jakob's law of UX from [16], it is often difficult to keep a clear communication as well as convey ideas to other team members. One approach would be to find a common prototyping tool with an easy-to-use interface. Another approach, considered in this paper, is to connect existing UIs familiar to the participants within one prototyping framework allowing people to continue using tools and views comfortable for them. Such connection of multiple UIs was implemented as a prototype with visual scripting, low-code, or no-code methods within the framework described in this paper.

A team of collaborators with different roles and skills, distributed in different locations, was able to perform effectively towards the concept development without compromising the completeness of the necessary features. The participants defined several interaction scenarios and checked their functional and technical feasibility providing guidance for their possible implementation. The usage of the RapPP platform was tested with the following selected scenarios: (a) design definition; (b) functionality identification; (c) safety cases analysis.

Next steps that will improve the functionality and usability of this prototyping platform shall include the integration of speech recognition in addition to the text recognition, integration of more existing user interfaces to check their compatibility, extend the understanding of more commands to cover more usage scenarios. Also, more visualization and feedback options should improve the usability of the platform, as it can be challenging to manage situations when too many participants interact simultaneously in one session. This also implies the need for the limitation definition during the interaction of multiple team members to make it better controllable.

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